

DIGITIZATION OF J. AUSTEN'S NOVEL "PRIDE AND PREJUDICE"

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Abstract: The use of various tools and technologies in the scholar study and in the literary and the appropriate use of those various techniques to complete the entire research study. It also described about the main theme of the famous work of Jane Austen "Pride and Prejudice" to convey the social norms for the middle-class families especially for the women. However, this is the romantic novel love is the main theme of this novel. The purpose of this research study how to digitalization helps in the researching various literary work along with providing various relevant information as well. It can be also mentioned that the main purpose is to describe about the theme of this literary work which delivers various information related to the social norms, integrity, the structure of various class and many others.

Keywords: Pride and Prejudice, Status of Women, Country House Novels, Characters, Socio-economic, Socio-cultural, Gender status, Discrimination.

1 Introduction

The research article is the masterpiece of Jane Austen named "Pride and prejudice". This novel is under the genre of 'Classic Regency Novel or Romance novel'. This piece of literary work is a non-fictional novel often characterized as the "Country House Novels". Austen's literature work is related to the fairy tale elements. This masterpiece reflects various social issues as well as themes of that particular time which includes war, the domestic lifestyle of the landed gentry of that particular time. This research study describes clearly the main theme of this literary work as well as the symmetrical review. Here also adding the analysis and discussion and literature review part to describe the entire theme of this literary work.

2 Literature Review

According to Burns, (2021), Jane Austen's Pride and Prejudice supports faith, ethics and denomination as well as opposed to enslavement when the slave trade has been already established. This literary work has become the abolitionist hallmark as it describes the pre and post-civil war situation and the condition of the slaves, condemning the slavery system and its attributes. On the other hand, Koyuncuoğlu, (2021), the use of various perspectives in this literary work analyzed various studies such as 'narrative perspective' as it creates dramatic tension for indicating the main theme of this novel. Here the focus is on the major character is Elizabeth Bennet through the manipulation of the characteristic perspective of Elizabeth maintained the unity of the novel (World Academy of Art & Science, n.d.). From the very beginning of the novel Elizabeth emerges as the focal character of the novel although focalization is not completely restricted to her. The use of focalization in this novel significantly contributes to developing the whole story. This story basically describes the social trend of that particular time about the reputation of women. Moreover, the story of this novel is related to how to overcome various obstacles for true love. It has been also described the class distinction of the society, the ultimate strength of the daily network, the status of the women in the society, behavior as well as integrity.

According to Bipasha, (2019), with the emergence of digitization, humanities scholars are always in need of more and more text and thus analyses the computational text as well. Digital texts are available from various sources. The first one is generally going through the preprocessing text and then transferring those texts into the standard format as well. This type of research study is concerned with three types of goals.

They are, building an automatic texts encoder, identifying the speakers as well as the characters from the literary work. Finally determining the appropriate context size while building a social network based work on the character interaction. On the other hand, Beard, et al. (2018), the component which is used daily in the digital age. This novel is still subject to copyright protection. Moreover, 'Pride and Prejudice' along with other literary works of Jane Austen makes use of digitalization such as copying, distribution of copyrighted content, modifying, leading to digital privacy and many others. Digitizing a literary work means makes it is under the copyright act to give protection for this along with other literary components. However, the main question is, Is Elizabeth Bennet has either prejudice or vanity. Elizabeth Bennet's behavior and her commitment to never sacrificing her value make it clear that the initial fault of all the characters is that pride and vanity are that the other is indulged in an obsessive degree. In this novel, the characteristic feature of the main protagonist, Elizabeth is obsessively vain and curiously distorted.

Table 1. Appropriateness of the title "Pride and Prejudice"

Measurement	Components
Cognitive	Use of English language fiction Begins with aphorism Community and cognition Communication skill Learning through the experiences Self-directed integration of knowledge Relationship management Information management
Integrative	Elizabeth's commitment to never sacrificing the value of women. Women's reputation is the utmost important part of the society Women's sense of integrity
Relationship	Communication and conversation Conflict management among the sisters and also with the gentlemen Relationship management and creating effort among the characters
Contextual	Time efficiency Working conditions among the characters
Ethical	Tolerance Respect towards the women of the society and other characters Emotional intelligence Responsibilities if the characters
Pride	A human trait The hero named Darcy embodied it
Prejudice	The heroin Elizabeth embodied it The human trait
Conveys the central message of the novel	Importance of women in society. Importance of love and maintaining relationships. Importance of all the classes-middle-upper and lower or slave class in the society.
Pride and Prejudice Prevail	In the characters In the activities of the characters
Social rank	Royalty Aristocracy or Nobility Upper-class Gentry Middle-class Gentry Working or lower class Army and navy-Non-commissioned officers, seaman, soldiers, commissioned officers, Marines and pensioners.

Source: Peterson (2018)

According to Burns, (2020), the chapter 1, this author has started this masterpiece with the conversation between Mr. Bennet and Mrs. Bennet about their new neighbor Mr. Bingley. Mr. Bingley is a single man of large fortune from the north of England and started to live on the side of Zombourn. In this chapter, the question which has been arisen from Mrs. Bennet about Bingley,

“is he married or single?” clears that Mrs. Bennet is looking for a wealthy gentleman for the five daughters of her. Bingley is perfect for one of those five daughters. On the other hand, the second and third chapters are introduced to a Merton ball party to which the Bennet family were invited. At this ball party, Bingley from the very first time started to like Jane, one of the daughters of Mr. and Mrs. Bennet. On the other hand, Szymańska, (2019), Mr. Darcy, who is a friend of Bingley from London, was addressed as “The proudest most disagreeable man in the world” by the daughters because of his unwillingness to dance with any girl of his own party. Mr. Fitzwilliam Darcy is another neighbor of the Bennet family and a potential suitor and wealthy gentleman (Deresiewicz, 1997). At this point, Mr. Bingley encouraged Darcy to dance with Elizabeth, one of the daughters of Mr. and Mrs. Bennet. At the same time, Darcy refused to dance because as per his opinion Elizabeth is beautiful but not that handsome to tempt Darcy as well. This conversation was heard by Elizabeth thus she also started to ignore Darcy from the beginning of the novel. Moreover, when Bingley (Miss Bingley and Mrs. Hurst) sisters when invites.

3 Materials and Methods

The methodology followed for this academic paper has been done following the qualitative methods. Thematic analysis has been done in a deductive approach and is a big part of the assessment method. The themes accessed in the statement is going to be analyzed using the positivism research Approach, Exploratory research design, Qualitative method of data collection of the secondary data and the non-profitability sampling method. This has been done because the thematic analysis of the observations is going to be done and positivism is the most appropriate design for the study. This allows the researcher to objectively analyze the secondary data collected and make for effective analysis of it. Similarly, the research design that has been used has been chosen to be the exploratory design as the exploration of the facts has been done to test if the digitalization of the novel written by “J. Austin” has been easier to read study and analyze for the different category of students.

The research is going to be done by analyzing the secondary research on the effectiveness of education done through the digital processes. The various nuances are going to be taken into consideration and accessed in terms of the way they are benefiting the students and the teachers and the form they are the most effective in. The main focus of the study is going to be on the digitalization of the novel of “pride and prejudice” and if the teachers and students prefer it to be in digital format or physical textbook format. This study is going to stress the preference of the individuals, as well as the secondary data analysis has been performed on the basis of a few set parameters:

- The understandability levels of the novel material for the students.
- The convenience and accessibility of the digitalized material.
- The psychological factors of the characters and relations between them.

The evaluation criteria have been set to access the convenience factor of the students and the teachers that allow them to perform their functions better or otherwise. This is to say that the evaluation is based on the study of if the teachers can teach better if the material is in digital format and if the students learn better if the material is in a digital format. Since the evaluation criteria are based on secondary research the assessment of many research papers done by the previous researchers has been accessed and the rating of the convenience and inconvenience factors are going to be given in the form of a rating based on the number of research papers that have been found advocating for and against the notion of digitalization of study materials.

However, there are two more factors that have been considered for this study that can be considered a part of the method is the

factor of language and teaching environment. In Ukraine, digitalization of the classrooms is an ongoing process and it is going to take some time to implement these changes (Lampiselkä, 2021). This contributes to the factors involving the digitalization process. Apart from that, the language factor has also been considered. The official language of Ukraine is Ukrainian and around 26% of the Ukrainian population are Russian speakers and study in Russian. The “Pride and Prejudice” novel being an English novel that is going to be translated into the local language has been considered as a factor influencing the convenience of the students and the teachers in terms of performing their duties. The results obtained from the evaluation and the assessment of these factors have been listed in detail and explained in the results section of the study.

4 Results

The evaluation process has yielded the results regarding the three themes:

4.1 Theme 1: Importance of desirable characters traits can be seen in the novel

The analysis of the collected data shows that the previous researchers have found that the characters of the Bennett sisters are more liked by the readers for their honorable disposition and a sense of self-respect that has been largely described by sociologists as a desirable quality for all individuals regardless of their gender and wealth. This is often compared by researchers to other novels of the same era as well (Armiatiet al. 2019). Whereas, Mr. Bingley is one of the characters that is rich but also very gentle and humble. This makes the character desirable and establishes him as the character of the prime focus of the story. Mr. Darcy on the other hand is the personification of the other kind of man that is wealthy but reserved. This makes everyone assume that he is very arrogant. The characters of the Bennett parents are very loud and portrayed to have fewer manners to indicate their less gentle demeanor of the lower class of the English society at that age.

Table 2. Showing the liking of the people based on the character traits

Criteria	Traits	Characters	Status
Desirability	Humbleness	Mr. Bingley	Main character
	Gentleness	Jane Mr. Bingley	Main character
Undesirability	self-respect	Jane, Elizabeth and Mr. Darcy	Main Character
	deceitfulness	George Wickham	Supporting Character
	Pride	Caroline Bingley	Supporting Character
	Gambling addiction	George Wickham	Supporting Character

The analysis of the character traits of the characters as well as the desirability of the individuals in that era in England, it is clear that Author Jane Austin has kept all the main characters with the desirable character traits while keeping the undesirable character traits for the characters that form the supporting roles. For the most part, it can be observed hence that the characters of the main roles have been hence highlighted among the other characters giving them more story coverage. The digitization of the story portrays this fact as the main characters get the most screen time. The understanding of the characters is enhanced by the digitization of the novel making the dynamics of the characters more possible and portraying the fact that to be desirable in the British society at that time one had to have these character traits. Apart from this, there is research conducted that says that the digitalization of books is necessary for the conservation of old literary works (Encheva et al. 2019).

The Ukrainian perspective: This formation of the characters can be noted as idealized and from a perspective of socio-economic background. The Ukrainian society also focuses on the same

principles of desirability or otherwise based on the personal character traits of the characters. This is the reason the digitalized copies of the novel has the potential to become popular among the Ukrainian people.

4.2 Theme 2: Effective Relationships dynamics can be seen between characters in the novel

The relationships between the characters are complex and ever-changing throughout the novel. Especially the characters of Elizabeth Bennett and Mr. Darcy. They start off disliking each other and eventually grow closer and fall in love with each other enough to get married (Menchaca, 2020). Whereas, the mother lead characters of Jane and Mr. Bingley started off with liking each other, then move on to grow distant (Glover & Tekreeti, 2018). Then get married in the end. The relationship between the character of Ms. Caroline Bingley and Elizabeth also start on a sour note but eventually gets warmer. The dynamics and the relationship between the characters are sophisticated and well portrayed (Alquraidhy, 2021). Real-life relations change based on many factors and it has been portrayed the same in the novel. The digitalization of the novel highlights the relation between the people even further and make for a great display of realism in the novel. The relationship between the characters shifts due to the various prejudices that exist among the characters as their mental block stops them from not seeing beyond their status to look for love. The characters also are shown to overstep their trait of self-respect into pride that also forms a factor for the changing status of relationships between the characters.

Table 3. Showing the preference of visual digitalization of studies

Criteria	Characters	Transition	End result
Relations	Jane and Mr. Bingley	Liking to separation then to love	Marriage
Factors affecting relationships	Misunderstanding and lack of communication		
Relations	Elizabeth and Mr. Darcy	Dislike to love	Marriage
Factors affecting relationships	Misunderstanding, pride and lack of communication		

It can be seen that the Characters are always shifting or making a transition from one state of being to another. The characters are being affected by their mental states and their disposition towards each other is also dictated by their personal sense of "pride and prejudice" This can be noted among the other side characters and the main characters as well. For example, the character of Caroline Bingley is hostile towards Elizabeth as they do not know each other and the former sees the latter as low value and responds with unkind words. The character of Mrs Benet and Elizabeth goes through a similar dimension shift in the novel.

The Ukrainian perspective: The people of Ukraine also largely come from humble backgrounds and compared to the people of that time could relate to even more humble lives. They could relate well to the characters and their situation.

4.3 Theme 3: Status of women in the earlier times

The status of women in the Victorian era and the later part of the Victorian era in Britain continued to a large extent to the time this novel was written. The digitization of the novel is going to help preserve this classic novel for future generations of people to read and experience.

The digitization also allows this work of art based on real-life feelings and character dynamics to be studied by sociologists to access many aspects of society. This also includes the character of the women characters that have been portrayed in the novel.

This portrayal did by the author also indicates the status of the women in that time. The theme of the story revolves around the main characters two of them are women. The main characters of Elizabeth and Jane, the two characters had to follow the patterns and rules prescribed by the society that they need to be well dressed and gentle (Chandioet al. 2019). For example, as the rain wet Elizabeth arrived at the estate of Mr. Bingley, Caroline out of pride made fun of her with harsh words. However, this novel also indicates that the ladies also held a strict set of rules to measure men by and men were also bound by the social rules and norms. However, the women were free to accept and reject the proposals of men based on their personal character traits.

The status of women is often a matter of debate among sociologists and the works of authors such as J. Austin are also critiqued to be overly idealized and not worth considering. However, it still makes for a good base for the study of societal norms and other things for students interested in that time and the gender equality of Ukrainian women (Kachynska, 2018). From a Ukrainian perspective, the women of Slavic origin enjoyed similar status in that era and it is easy for them to relate to the characters in the story (Khromeychuk, 2018).

5 Discussion

Digitization has been considered the most significant technology trend of recent time. Nowadays, all the firms are under the pressure of using digital technologies as much as possible. However, going digitally evokes many types of benefits. Though it requires investments as well as associated costs as well. It also provides noticeable progress of digital technologies. The main focus is to illustrate the recent state of this art in order to provide a better understanding of the digitalization terms. Moreover, digitalization literature provides a clear understanding of the foundation in regards to the achieved advancements as per the last few years. There are also included many additional debates on the need for digitalization agenda for the future development of the research procedures (Reis et al., 2019). In the modern age digitalization is a recent topic. The significant use of this digitalization procedure for a literary work to be copyright protection to the research work of many researchers on this particular masterpiece of J. Austen. However, going digital means finding relevant information from internet searching. However, for maintaining academic integrity there are implemented copyright protection issues to project this literary work.

It is easy to find relevant articles from the internet and take various help from that article for search work. The major issue is the how-to protect those articles from misuse of them. However, this literary work deals with the various social norms of that particular time. Jane Austen's 'Pride and Prejudice' is a famous literary work. Moreover, Digital Humanities is the era of scholarly activities at the intersections of digital technologies as well as the discipline of humanities.

It also can be accepted that DH is the new way of doing the scholarship that involves transdisciplinary, computationally engaged research, collaborative, teaching procedures and others. Here includes digital tools and various methods to the humanities study. It makes new kid of techniques and teaching procedures as well. This is accepted by the researcher that the new technologies help us to understand vastly the history of the literature work and its language. Various tools are there to underwood to the change of the genre as well as the stereotypes in the literary works (Reis et al., 2019). The collection of the icon class which are the classification system that describes the art. This allows the researchers to search for more relevant images and information on the research topic.

Basically, the theme of this novel is about the culture of the society of that particular time of pre and post-civil war. According to the rules of that time, social norms women have no right on the property of their parents. The property is always

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